

ASSESSMENT OF WOMEN'S SENSITISATION ON CLIMATE CHANGE IN LAGOS STATE

Ojeleye Dorcas A.^{1*}, Adejobi Samson O.¹ and Folami Maria M.¹

¹Department of Geography and Planning, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos, Nigeria

*Corresponding author email: ayoomolayo07@gmail.com

Abstract

The dilemma of climate change and its impacts calls for collaboration in tackling this plague confronting the present generation. The impact of climate change is experienced differently by regions, ages, communities, races, and gender, thereby putting women in many communities at the receiving end of being the most vulnerable. The study assessed the level of women's sensitisation on climate change awareness in Lagos State. Using a purposive sampling technique, primary data were collected with the help of a structured questionnaire administered to Two hundred, and Seventy-two (272) respondents in the Ikeja Local Government Area. Of these, 89.0% were retrieved and found useful for analysis. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistical tools such as mean, bar graph, percentage, standard deviation, and frequency count. The results reveal that 86.0% of the respondents were aware of climate change. 80.2% of the respondents confirmed the reality of climate change. The result also showed that only 29.0% of the respondents were able to ascertain other women's awareness of climate change in their communities. A larger percentage (60.3%) of the respondents heard about climate change through the mass media. However, the result of the study shows that 29.0% of the respondents have community programmes occasionally organised within their location for the enlightenment of people on climate change and environmental issues. The paper concludes by recommending that community initiatives and programmes towards enlightening and training people, especially women and girls, on climate change and other environmental issues should be adopted at the grassroots.

Keywords: Climate Change, Community, Initiative, Vulnerable, Environment, Grassroots

1.0 Introduction

Climate change has been one of the most challenging issues confronting this 21st-century. The reality emerged from its consequent impacts on people due to various human activities that continue to worsen the consequences. Globally, all efforts are being engaged to tackle the aftermath of the impact at the regional, state, and local levels. However, communal efforts as regards climate change awareness on the causes, effects, and adaptive measures for people at the grassroots are crucial to sustainable human and environmental development. According to United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, climate change is referred to as a change, attributable directly to human activities which alter the composition of the global temperature in addition to natural climate variability observed over a considerable period (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC (2007) and World Health Organisation (2016).

Odjugo (2009) identified two ways of climate change occurrences relative to climatic warming and cooling. Climatic cooling is when the temperature of the system or region exhibits a continuously declining trend over a considerable period, while the reverse is true for climate

warming. However, two basic factors were further identified as causes of climate change. These are natural processes (biogeographical) and human activities (anthropogenic). The natural processes involved astronomical factors, which include changes in the eccentricity of the Earth's orbit, changes in the obliquity of the plane of the ecliptic, and changes in orbital procession. Extraterrestrial factors include solar radiation quality and quantity. The anthropogenic factor in climate change involves human activities which either emit large amounts of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and deplete the ozone layer, or activities that reduce the amount of carbon absorbed from the atmosphere.

In the last twenty years, the total warming effect from greenhouse gasses added by anthropogenic activities to the earth atmosphere increased by 51 percent (U.S Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA), 2025). This is due to human activities that induced the change and caused the earth's average temperature to rise. The changing climate patterns have a significant impact on our planet, as the world is about 1.19°C (2.14°F) warmer than the pre-industrial era. The North and South Poles are warming three times faster than the rest of the world, and Antarctica is losing 1 billion metric tons of ice every 40 hours. Sea levels have risen by 9 inches over the past century, with storms, droughts, floods, forest fires, and heat waves growing intensely as a result of warmer temperatures and rising sea levels (Guardian, 2020; Connor, 2020; and Global Citizen, 2023).

On account of this, the level of climate change impacts on variability among regions, communities, classes, income groups, and gender requires community involvement. Climate change has a serious negative effect on every ramification of human life, such as food, health, water resources, biodiversity, human settlement, and migration patterns, due to environmental degradation (United Nations Women and Climate Fact Sheet, 2022). However, the impact of climate change on gender is not the same as discovered globally. Women are increasingly viewed to be more vulnerable than men to the impacts of climate change due to their different and unequal social roles and status (Mohajan, 2022; United Nations Women, 2025).

Joe McCarthy (2020) reveal that heat waves, droughts, rising sea levels, and extreme storms affect women disproportionately. This is because women are more likely to live in poverty than men, have less access to basic human rights like having the ability to freely move and acquire land, and face systematic violence that escalates during periods of instability (Global Citizen, 2020). Other factors identified that make women vulnerable to climate change include:

- Seventy percent of 1.3 billion people living in poverty conditions happen to be women.
- Forty percent of the poorest households in urban areas are headed by women with women predominating the world's food production (with a ratio 50-80 percent), but they own less than 10 percent of the land.
- Women, particularly in rural areas, represent a high percentage of poor communities that are highly dependent on local natural resources for their livelihood, where they shoulder major responsibility for household water supply, energy for cooking, heating, and food security.
- Women have limited access to environmental goods, services and control. They are not involved in the distribution of environmental management benefits and neglected to participate in decision-making. This consequently makes women incapacitated to confront climate change (United Nations Chronicles, 2009).

The factors above reveal that the more climate change intensifies, the more women struggle. Therefore, the severity of incapacitation women and girls could be subjected to in the future due to climate change impacts at the moment necessitates community involvement in climate change sensitisation at the grassroots.

Several studies have been carried out on the effects of climate change on the livelihood of women, women's perception and knowledge of climate change, women and girls' vulnerability to climate change, women's strategies for adaptation to climate change, and climate variability in water-scarce areas (Otufale and Ose, 2017; Nalwanga *et al.*, 2021; Marwa, 2021; Jemima *et al.*, 2022; Haque *et al.*, 2023; Masoumeh and Dariush, 2023; Food and Agricultural Organisation, 2024; Adejobi and Ojeleye, 2024). However, none of these studies focussed on assessment of women sensitisation on climate change awareness. This study will fill the gap in the literature. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to examine women's awareness of climate change and the reality of its happening, the mode through which the women heard about climate change and the level of community involvement in sensitising people on climate change and other environmental issues.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Study area

The study area is Ikeja, the capital city of Lagos State in Southwestern Nigeria. Lagos State is located between latitudes 6° 23'N and 6° 41'N, and longitudes 2° 42'E and 3° 42'E. It is bounded in the North and East by Ogun State, in the South by the Atlantic Ocean/ Gulf of Guinea, and in the West by the Republic of Benin. Lagos State comprises 20 Local Government Areas.

Ikeja has a tropical climate with most of the months in the year experiencing heavy rainfall of about 1645 mm (64.8 inches) each year. The Köppen-Geiger scale rates this climatic area as Am. AM is a sub-classification under the A group which has warm temperatures with the warmest average temperature above 18°C. Ikeja's typical temperature is 26.4 °C, and the brief dry season has very little impact on the climate as a whole. Moreover, due to the proximity of the city to the equator, the hottest period in Ikeja is imprecise but usually experienced around January, July, August, September, October, November, and December in the year.

The daily average temperature is above 32.2°F, while the hot season lasts for 4.4 months, from December 12 to April 25. Ikeja experiences its warmest month of the year in March, with an average high of 32.7°C and low of 25.5°C. The daily average maximum temperature is below 28.8°C, with the chilly season lasting 3.2 months, from June 23 to September 30. The month of August is the coldest month of the year in Ikeja, with an average low of 23.3°C and a high of 27.7°C.

2.2 Research Design, Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Assessment of women sensitisation on climate change was carried out among women in Ikeja, Ikeja Local Government Area, Lagos State. The study area was selected as the seat of the state government and the commercial hub of the nation. The study was conducted using a survey method. A purposive sampling method was used to select the women for the survey. The method was found suitable as the sample for the study (women) shared similar traits, such as life experiences that the study focussed on. A total population of 110,387 women in the study area

was used to obtain a sample size of 272 using the formula for determining the sample size recommended by (Jemima *et al.*, 2022).

$$\frac{Z^2 * P(1-P)}{e^2}$$

$$1 + \frac{Z^2 * P(1-P)}{e^2 N}$$

Where Z = Confidence Level (Z = 90% confidence level = 1.65).

N = Population to be Sampled (110, 387 women).

e = Margin error (e=5% (0.05).

P = Percentage probability of false rejecting the null hypothesis (e=50% (0.05).

$$= \frac{1.65^2 * (0.5(1 - 0.5/0.5))}{0.05^2}$$

$$1 + \frac{(1.65^2 * 0.5(1 - 0.5/0.5))}{0.05^2 * 110, 387}$$

$$= \frac{272}{1000}$$

$$1000$$

A total number of 272 copies of questionnaire was administered to women in the study area out of which a total number of two hundred and forty-two (242) questionnaires were retrieved and found useful for analysis. Data were analysed using frequency count, bar graph, means, and percentages.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Distribution of Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 reveals the socio-economic characteristics of the women interviewed. The result revealed that more than (90.0%) of the women interviewed are between the age range 18 and 58 years in which the passion to learn and adopt new innovations and skills are certainly achievable, especially in the area of climate change. This study established the facts behind the Campaign for Girls and Women’s Education (CAMFED, 2025) campaign for girls and women education on climate change impacts and empowerment.

The marital status of the women reveals that more than average (53.3%) of the respondents is still single. This established further the tendency for women to effectively engage in other activities that could add value to them and the community at large.

The examination of the women’s educational status revealed that 1.2 % had no formal education, 4.6% had primary education, 37.9% had secondary education, 34.9% had acquired B.Sc. 4.1% are M.Sc. certificate holders, 0.8% have Doctoral degree certificates, and 16.6% have degrees in National Diploma, National Certificate of Education, or its equivalent. The study reveals that more than 95.0% of the women had basic education. This could have imparted their perception of climate change. This supports Ojeleye *et al.* (2019), where a more-than-average number of the women interviewed were educated enough to contribute to issues on climate change. However, the Campaign for Female Education (CAMFED, 2025) revealed the negative impact lack of

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of the Urban Women

Survey	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-24	90	37.2
	25-31	29	12.0
	32-38	36	14.9
	39-44	41	16.9
	45-51	24	9.9
	52-58	16	6.6
	59-67	6	2.5
Marital	Married	111	45.9
	Single	129	53.3
	Widow	2	0.8
Education	No formal Education	3	1.2
	Primary Education	11	4.6
	Secondary Education	91	37.8
	B.Sc.	84	34.9
	M.Sc.	10	4.1
	Ph.D	2	0.8
	Others	40	16.6
Occupation	Civil Servant	31	12.9
	Private Organisation's employee	22	9.1
	Trader	41	17.0
	Entrepreneur	54	22.4
	Apprentices	4	19.9

	Others	45	18.7
Income	Less than ₦50,000	162	67.2
	₦50,000 - ₦ 99,000	45	18.7
	₦100,000 - ₦199,00	22	9.1
	₦200,000 - ₦299,000	5	2.1
	₦300,000 - ₦399,000	7	2.9

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2024)

education could have on girls' and women. The report from this source (Campaign for Female Education (CAMFED, 2025) established that girls and women excluded from education are more likely to suffer injury or death in case of climate disaster. This revealed the significance of education for women and girls in order to cope with the aftermath of climate change.

Assessment of the women's occupation in the study area revealed that 12.9% of the urban women were civil servants, 9.1% were private organisation employees, 17.0% were traders, 22.4% were entrepreneurial who owned their businesses, 19.9% were apprentices, 18.7% accounted for those engaged in other activities such as urban agriculture, residential aids to earn a living. This finding agreed with Campaign for Female Education (CAMFED, 2024) based on twenty-five years of research experience in Africa, which showcased educated women's ability to run and grow sustainable businesses, such as climate-smart agriculture successfully. This is a good indicator for women's participation in climate change action.

On the income of the women, the study revealed that 67.2% of the women earn below ₦50,000.00. 18.7% of the women earn between ₦50,000.00 and ₦99,000.00. 9.1% of the women earn between ₦100,000.00 and ₦199,000.00. 2.1% of the women earn between ₦200,000.00 and ₦299,000.00, while 2.9% of the women earn between ₦300,000:00 and ₦399,000:00. This reveals that the majority (67.2%) of the women sampled are buoyant economically. This should be put into consideration during adoption of climate change action. Any mitigation and adaptation measures to be put in place to curtail climate change impacts should not be taxing on women's income for the measure(s) to be adopted and effective.

3.2 Distribution of Respondents' Awareness of Climate Change

Table 2 shows that 86.0% of urban women were aware of climate change, while 14.0% indicated their unawareness of climate change. However, 80.2% of the respondents in the study area were certain that climate change is happening. 5.4% of the urban women revealed negative notions about climate change happening, while 14.5% were not sure of climate change happening. The outcome of this study reveals that more than seventy-five percent of urban women in the study area were aware of climate change and its happening. This is a good indicator and could play a significant role in achieving effective sensitization and training of women about climate change.

Table 2: Urban Women’s Perception and Reality of Climate Change

	Yes	No	Not sure	Total
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Recent Awareness on Climate change	208(86.0)	34(14)	-	242(100)
Reality of Climate Change Happening	194(80.2)	13(5.4)	35(14.5)	242(100)

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork (2024)

3.3 Women’s Mode of Information of Climate Change

Figure 1 reveals various modes through which the women interviewed heard about climate change. 60.3% of the women heard through mass media only. 9.1% of the women heard through seminars/conferences. 6.2% of the women heard through community programs. 7.4% of the women heard through mass media, seminars, and conferences, 13.6% of the women heard about climate change through other means such as friends, relatives, and family members, while 3.3% of the women are unaware of climate change. The findings reveal the positive impact mass media is having on the public in the area of information dissemination to people on climate change. However, the study reveals lesser achievements in the use of conferences, seminars, and community programs in actualizing effective communication to people on climate change.

Figure 1: Women’s Mode of Information of Climate Change

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork (2024)

3.4 Breakdown of Respondents' Opinion on Impacts of Climate Change

Table 3 reveals the descriptive analysis on women's opinion over present and future impacts of climate change globally. The result shows that the total mean value is 2.25, while the standard deviation is 1.43. The Mean figure varies from 1.80 – 2.7, while the Standard Deviation ranges from 1.33 – 1.59. An increase in sea level has the highest mean, while the increase in temperature globally has the lowest mean. The response from the table shows an increase in global sea level, which indicates an increase in the occurrences of various related environmental disasters such as flooding, erosion, and poor water quality. The consequences further put food production, human health, and the ecosystem at serious risk, as established by (Johnson and William, 2023; National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), 2025). This reveals that the consequences of the increase in global level will definitely increase women's vulnerability (United Nations Women and Climate Fact Sheet, 2022). Hence, the need for women's sensitisation and training on climate change.

Table 3: Women's Opinion on Present and Future Impacts of Climate Change Globally

Present and future Impacts of Climate Change Globally	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Increase in temperature globally	1	5	1.8	1.33
Overall decrease in global portable water	1	5	2.26	1.33
Increase in incidence and intensity of heat	1	5	2.07	1.42
Increase in the rate of extinction of plant and animal species	1	5	2.28	1.5
Overall decrease in global food production	1	5	2.23	1.45
Increase in global sea level	1	5	2.71	1.59
Increase in intensity of storm across regions	1	5	2.43	1.45

Keys: 1 = Very likely; 2 = Somewhat; 3 = Somewhat unlikely; 4 = Not likely ; 5 = I don't know

3.5 Respondents' Sensitisation on Issues of Climate Change

Table 4 reveals women's observations on sensitisation of people at the communal level through various community programmes on climate change and environmental issues. The study reveals that 12.1% of the women do have community programmes occasionally organised for sensitising people in their communities. 54.0% of the women gave a negative response, while 33.9% of the women were not sure whether their communities do organise such programmes or not. However, the opinion of women on sensitisation of women and people in the community on climate change

revealed that 29.0% of the women have such programs organised in their communities. 59.0% of the women did not have such a programme in their communities, while 20.1% of the women were not sure if at any point in time a program to enlighten or sensitize people on climate change was organized. This reveals that much has not been achieved at our grassroots in the area of informing people about climate change and environmental issues. This is contrary to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2022) agenda on developing community-based, low-carbon, climate-resilient solutions for investing in vulnerable populations (such as indigenous peoples, youth, women, and persons with disabilities) affected by climate change.

Table 4: Community Programmes on Climate Change and Environmental Issues

Enlightenment through Community Programmes on:	Yes	No	Not sure
Environmental Issues	29(12.1%)	129(54.0%)	81(33.9%)
Climate Change	50(29.0%)	141(59.0%)	48(20.1%)

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2024)

3.6 *Obstacles to Climate Change Awareness* Figure 2 reveals various factors identified by women as obstacles to climate change awareness in our communities. The study shows that 11.5% of the women indicated climate change denial. 30.2% of the women indicated a focus on other challenges of life. 15.3% of the women indicated the economic cost of reducing greenhouse gases. 4.7% indicated the politics of mitigation, while 38.3% indicated all the factors as obstacles to climate change awareness in our communities. The study reveals that meeting the present needs of people is crucial to achieving effective climate change awareness and adoption of mitigation and adaptation measures.

Figure 2: Obstacles to Climate Change Awareness in Our Communities

Source: Author's Fieldwork (2024)

3.7 Respondents' Opinion on Other Women in the Communities' Awareness of Climate Change

Figure 3 reveals women's opinions of other women in our communities' awareness of climate change. 29.0% of the women reveal that other women in their communities are aware of climate change. 24.4% of the women disagreed with other women in their communities' awareness of climate change. However, a larger percentage of the women (46.6%) were not certain whether other women in their communities were aware of climate change or not. The study indicates that a lot still needs to be achieved at the grassroots in the area of enlightenment and sensitisation of people on the issue of climate change

Figure 3: Other Women in the Communities' Awareness of Climate Change

Source: Author's Fieldwork (2024)

4.0 Conclusion

The study evaluated women's sensitisation on climate change awareness in Lagos State. The roles that communities play in the area of enlightening and sensitising people on environmental issues and climate change through the use of various community programmes were assessed. The study reveals that a larger proportion of the respondents were aware of climate change and its reality. Women who heard of climate change through the mass media dominated the entire population sampled in the study area and a larger percentage of the women revealed that all the factors: climate denial, focus on other challenges, cost of reducing greenhouse gas, and politics of mitigation are the major obstacles to climate change awareness in our communities. The study reveals that much has not been achieved at the community level in the area of climate change awareness and sensitization. The findings on women who were not sure of other women in their communities' awareness of climate change further confirm the low level of performance at the grassroots in the area of climate change sensitization for women and other groups susceptible to climate change impacts.

5.0 Recommendations

The study, therefore, recommends adoption of community-based initiatives and programmes that focus on addressing the issue of the vulnerable. Joint community efforts will help in developing climate change resilience programmes favourable and beneficial to people in the community. Community leaders should collaborate with stakeholders, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and individuals in the community to achieve effective climate change sensitisation, awareness, education, and empowerment of women and girls, the most vulnerable group of climate change impacts. This is key to achieving sustainable environmental development. Therefore, all avenues should be made available by the government for people to have constant and unrestricted access to information on climate change and environmental issues. Implementation of a bottom-up approach in building effective climate change resilience directed towards the well-being of the vulnerable groups, especially women and girls in our communities, will achieve good success if adopted.

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